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Effectiveness of two types of Protected Areas (PAs) for plant species diversity and conservation in Southwestern, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Protected Areas (PAs) play a crucial role in conserving biodiversity. The study assessed the effectiveness of two types of PAs in conserving forest biodiversity. Therefore, the study quantified and compared species diversity in the SNR (Queen's Plot of Akure Forest Reserve) and NP (Okomu National Park) in Southwestern, Nigeria. Systematic line transects were used to establish plots of 900 m² at 200 m intervals based on PAs sizes. 15 plots were established in SNR and 15 in NP. Trees with Diameter at breast height (Dbh) ≥ 10 cm were identified with their heights and diameters recorded. Shannon-Wiener (H'), Simpson's evenness indices (1-D) and Margalef (SR) were computed using PAST software. 773 trees with Dbh ≥ 10 cm were identified in the two PAs (266 trees, 44 species and 21 families in SNR, 507 trees, 67 species and 28 families in NP). The mean Dbh and height (40.65; 32.5) in SNR were higher than (28.2; 26.84) in NP. The mean Dbh was statistically different between the two PAs types with $p = 0.003$. The H' , 1-D, and SR (3.47; 0.94; 9.91) in NP were higher than in SNR (3.19; 0.93; 7.88). The findings revealed that Okomu National Park exhibited higher biodiversity indices across all metrics compared to the Queen's Plot. Further inferential statistics indicated a significant difference in the Shannon-Wiener and Margalef species richness indices between the two PAs, implying NP is effective in conserving forest biodiversity than SNR. The study recommends integrated conservation approaches that combine strict protection with multi-use strategies to leverage their unique strength to maximize biodiversity outcomes.

Keywords: Conservation, ecosystem, forest biodiversity, height, multiple use, plant species, Protected Areas (PAs), Okomu National Park, Akure Forest Reserve

1. INTRODUCTION

Tropical rainforests are repositories of biodiversity harbouring more than half of all biodiversity, containing over 50% of the World described and many undeclared species. They play important role in carbon sequestration, hydrological cycle (Toru and Kibret, 2019). They also help reduce and/ prevent natural disasters such as flood and drought. They improve air quality and human psychological well-being by enhancing the environment's air quality and physical appearance (Ojha *et al.*, 2019). Forests are also vital in ensuring food security for rural communities, with over 250 million people in the Tropical region depending on them. Moreover, forests and inhabiting tree species contribute to achieving 28 targets relating to the 10 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as they play many roles in different areas of development (Jones *et al.*, 2018, Safar *et al.*, 2020).

Biodiversity loss is one of the worst impacts of human activities on Earth's ecosystem. The current extinction rates are 100 to 1000 times higher than their background value. The current pace and rates of biodiversity loss have been attributed to the pressure inflicted on natural system due to human activities (Nila *et al.*, 2019). In fact, about 75% of the Earth surface has been altered by human activities which are strongly associated with biodiversity loss.

As a measure to limit human activities and provide safe spaces for nature to thrive, Protected Areas (PAs) have become crucial instruments in minimizing the human footprint (Nila *et al.*, 2019). PAs are designated land or sea areas managed to safeguard biodiversity and preserve natural and cultural resources. The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has developed a categorization system for PAs based on their allowable human activities and management objectives. There is the Strict Nature Reserves (SNRs). SNRs are designated for scientific research and wilderness protection, aiming to preserve pristine ecosystems, rare species, and unique ecological features. However, these reserves can restrict local communities' access to forest resources (Orimaye *et al.*, 2020). We also have Natural Parks; these are large areas protected to support various species, habitats, and ecological processes. These parks balance conservation with economic development through tourism and recreation, ensuring that conservation efforts are not compromised. Approximately 17% of the Earth's surface has been designated as PAs (Ajayi and Ayodele, 2018). Consequently, the proliferation and management efficiency of PAs worldwide has become increasingly significant. However, growing evidence suggests that despite the increasing number of PAs, biodiversity loss continues to worsen, and human pressure is rising both within and outside these areas (Leclere *et al.*, 2020).

Several studies have used case studies to support their arguments, but it remains unclear to what extent these case studies are representative of the IUCN categories. Their findings are often inconclusive. For instance, some studies (Nelson and Chomitz, 2011) argue that Strict Nature Reserves (SNRs) are more effective than multiple-use areas, while others (Miranda *et al.*, 2016) observe the opposite. Yet other studies (Anderson and Mammides, 2019) find no significant difference in their effectiveness in conserving biodiversity. Several factors may account for these contrasting observations. First, the studies may compare PAs in dissimilar ways, often focusing on different regions (Geldmann *et al.*, 2019) or using various statistical methods, which, while appropriate, are not without biases.

Consequently, this study aims to examine the effectiveness of two types of PAs by using ecological indices of species diversity and richness within the same region in southwestern Nigeria. Specifically, it focuses on Queen's Plot of Akure Forest Reserve, designated as a Strict

Nature Reserve (SNR), and Okomu National Park, designated as a Natural Park. These areas were chosen because their conservation objectives and levels of allowable human interference align with the IUCN classification.

2. METHODOLOGY

2. 1. Study Area

2. 1. 1. Queen’s Plot of Akure Forest Reserve

The Queen’s Plot of Akure Forest Reserve is situated within Akure Forest Reserve, located in Ondo State, south west, Nigeria. (Orimaye *et al.*, 2020). The area experiences distinct dry (November-February) and rainy seasons (March-October), with a bimodal annual precipitation of about 2500 mm, temperatures ranging from 21 °C to 29 °C and average relative humidity of 80-85% relative humidity. Soils are acidic to slightly neutral (pH 6.7-7.3). The area is known for its moist semi-deciduous vegetation, including trees like African mahogany and African walnut, reaching heights of 40 meters (Adeduntan and Olusola, 2013).

Figure 1. Queen’s Plot of Akure Forest Reserve and Surrounding communities Okomu National Park.

Okomu National Park is located 75 kilometers west of Benin City in Edo State, Nigeria. it lies between latitudes 6°15' N to 6°25' N and longitudes 5°90' E to 5°25' E (Osabiya *et al.*, 2022). The terrain is predominantly low-lying, with elevations ranging from 30 to 60 meters above sea level. The climate features a monthly average temperature of 30.2 °C and consistently high relative humidity, typically above 65% (Ajayi and Ayodele, 2018). Vegetation within the park includes Guinea-Congo lowland rainforest, fresh swamp forests along rivers, and various forest types supporting emergent trees and diverse wildlife (Osabiya *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 2. Okomu National Park and Surrounding Communities.

2. 2. Vegetation Sampling and Measurement

2. 2. 1. Tree Inventory Data Collection

To collect data on species composition, forest structure, tree species richness, and diversity, a ground-based inventory was conducted following the systematic line transect method used by (Adekunle *et al.*, 2013a). This approach enabled gathering detailed information on the growth characteristics of individual tree species in the study areas.

2. 2. 2. Sample Plot Demarcation

To mitigate the edge effects of the forest, transects were established at least 10 meters away from the forest boundary. The GPS coordinates of each transect were recorded using a

handheld GPS device. In each study site, we set up parallel transects, each 750 meters long and spaced 200 meters apart. Along these transects, 30 m × 30 m plots were demarcated at 200 meter intervals (Figure 3). Consequently, 15 plots were assessed at the Queen’s plot of Akure Forest Reserve representing the SNR and 45 plots in Okomu National Park representing the NP. Within each plot, all trees with a Diameter at Breast Height (Dbh) ≥ 10 cm were identified and measured.

Figure 3. Schematic Diagram of Plot Locations using Systematic Line Transect.

2. 2. 3. Identification of Tree Species

Every tree species found in each sample plot was identified by a taxonomist using their scientific names where the botanical name was not immediately known; the trees were identified by their local or commercial names (Ige *et al.*, 2013). To ensure accurate identification, leaves, fruits, and bark samples were collected and sent to the Forestry Herbarium at the Nigerian Forestry Research Institute in Ibadan.

Measurement and information collected are diameter at breast height (Dbh) of >10 cm, diameter at the base, middle, and the top including total and merchantable heights were collected using a Spiegel Relascope and diameter girth tape.

2. 3. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, species diversity indices of Shannon-Wiener index, Simpson diversity index and Margalef (Species richness). These were subjected to inferential statistics.

2. 3. 1. Shannon-Wiener Index of Diversity (H')

This index helps quantify the diversity within a community, taking into account both the number of species present and the evenness of their distribution. The Shannon-Wiener Index of Diversity (H') was calculated using the formula:

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^S PiLnPi \quad (1)$$

where: H = Shannon-Wiener index of diversity, S = The total number of species present in the community, Pi = The proportion of 's' represented by the ith species, Ln = natural log

2. 3. 2. Simpson's Diversity Index (1-D)

This index measures the probability that two individuals randomly selected from a sample will belong to different species. It considers both species richness (the number of species) and species evenness (the relative abundance of each species). The value ranges from 0 to 1.0 with higher value indicating greater diversity. It was computed using the formula:

$$D = 1 - \left(\frac{n(n-1)}{N(N-1)} \right) \quad (2)$$

where: n = The cumulative count of individuals belonging to a particular species in the community, N = Total number of individuals across all species.

2. 3. 3. Margalef index

The Margalef index is a measure of species richness used in ecology to assess the biodiversity of a community, ecosystem, or geographic area. It accounts for the number of species present (S) and the total number of individuals (N) in the sample. The Margalef index (SR) is was calculated using the formula:

$$SR = \frac{S}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (3)$$

where: SR = Margalef index, S = Overall count of species, N = cumulative number of individuals

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Species Composition and Diversity in the Two Protected Area Types

The trees encountered at the research sites are typical of tropical forests (Osabiya *et al.*, 2022) The majority of tree species are economically important tropical hardwoods, indicating that these forests are valuable habitats for native tropical hardwoods.

The NP exhibits higher species richness (63 species, 28 families) than the SNR (44 species, 21 families). These findings align with studies such as Akinrinola *et al.*, 2014, which highlight that National Parks often host more diverse flora due to less stringent restrictions that allow moderate human interaction and promote ecological heterogeneity.

In contrast, the SNR, being more restrictive, limits ecological interactions that might facilitate species introductions, leading to lower diversity. However, SNRs are crucial for preserving endemic and sensitive species, as noted by Kayombo *et al.*, 2022.

Table 1. Species Composition and Diversity in the Strict Nature of Akure Forest Reserve and Okomu National Park.

Species	Frequency	Diameter at breast height(cm)	Tree Height (m)
<i>Albizia zygia</i>	3	48.3	31.4
<i>Anonidium manni</i>	2	26.6	12.6
<i>Anthonatha macrophylla</i>	2	23.6	20.5
<i>Bhighia sapida</i>	1	13.5	13
<i>Bosqueia angolensis</i>	7	24.1	25.6
<i>Brachystegia eurycoma</i>	5	83.9	34.8
<i>Canthium hispidium</i>	1	17.7	29
<i>Celtis mildbreadi</i>	2	39.6	17.3
<i>Celtis zenkeri</i>	18	40.03	29.6
<i>Chrysophyllum albidum</i>	1	35	53
<i>Chrysophyllum cainito</i>	11	54.1	44.6
<i>Cleistopholis patens</i>	2	45.1	34.1
<i>Cola cordifolia</i>	1	27.5	14.8
<i>Cola gigantean</i>	7	60.2	34.4
<i>Cola millenni</i>	4	17.9	25.9
<i>Cordia millennii</i>	14	36.1	32.6
<i>Desplatsia lutea</i>	1	28.5	23
<i>Diospyros dendo</i>	1	16	23.2
<i>Diospyros canaliculata</i>	2	30.4	15.9
<i>Diospyros dendo</i>	5	24.3	35.9
<i>Drypetes gilgiana</i>	4	16.9	23.8
<i>Entandropragma angolense</i>	18	57.8	85.8
<i>Funtimia elastica</i>	8	23.4	23.9
<i>Hildegardis bateri</i>	2	72.7	97.8
<i>Irvingia wombulu</i>	1	62.5	38

<i>Khaya grandifolia</i>	6	37.9	36.2
<i>Khaya ivorensis</i>	7	64.3	31.4
<i>Macaranga capensis</i>	2	27.1	30
<i>Malacantha alnifolia</i>	1	20.1	14
<i>Mansonia altissima</i>	29	36.6	46.4
<i>Milicia excelsa</i>	3	54.1	35.7
<i>Monodora tenuifolia</i>	1	30.8	33
<i>Nesogordonia papeverifa</i>	3	24.1	21.03
<i>Pentaclethra macrpphylla</i>	2	48.1	19.5
<i>Piptadeniastrum africanum</i>	1	29.5	39.5
<i>Pterygota macrocarpa</i>	1	72.9	35
<i>Pycanthus angolensis</i>	2	45.5	36.8
<i>Ricinodendron hendolittis</i>	1	130	44
<i>Spondia mombin</i>	1	18.3	33
<i>Sterculia rhinopetala</i>	36	40.1	33.8
<i>Strombosia pustulata</i>	26	37.8	28.7
<i>Terminalia superb</i>	9	57.6	42
<i>Trichilia monadelphpha</i>	2	16.9	13.4
<i>Triplochiton scleroxylon</i>	9	71.7	38.8
<i>Xlopia aethiopica</i>	1	40.4	29.8

Table 2. Species Composition and Diversity in the Okomu National Park.

Species	Frequency	Diameter at breast height (cm)	Tree Height (m)
<i>Afzelia africana</i>	6	15.95	22.63
<i>Albizia zygia</i>	2	27.2	25
<i>Allanblancka floribunda</i>	77	24.06	24.94
<i>Allophylus africanus</i>	4	16.65	20.8
<i>Alstonia bonnie</i>	19	32.66	26.31
<i>Amphimas pterocarpoides</i>	1	62	39

<i>Anonodium mannii</i>	8	17.25	17.73
<i>Anonyxis klaineana</i>	7	41.61	40.81
<i>Anthocleista vogelii</i>	2	21	26.75
<i>Anthonatha macrophylla</i>	7	16.28	19.49
<i>Baphia nitida</i>	4	28.56	25.68
<i>Barteria fistulosa</i>	7	13.18	18.77
<i>Bombax buonopozene</i>	1	54	49
<i>Bridelia micrantha</i>	2	32.25	33.75
<i>Buchholza coriacea</i>	2	17.75	22.5
<i>Canarium schweinfurthii</i>	6	18.35	21.08
<i>Canthium subcordatum</i>	13	22.64	24.91
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	2	30.8	24.3
<i>celtis zenkeri</i>	3	17.33	29.07
<i>Cleistopholis patens</i>	5	38.92	32.9
<i>Cola millenni</i>	6	16.43	20.62
<i>Daniellia ogea</i>	6	26.22	26.1
<i>Dicapyros piscatorial</i>	1	28.8	18.2
<i>Diospyrus crassiflora</i>	4	19.4	25.75
<i>Distemonanthus benthamianus</i>	1	14.8	23
<i>Entandrophragma angolense</i>	2	42.25	54.5
<i>Entandrophragma candollei</i>	1	17.7	23
<i>Entandrophragma cylindricum</i>	5	36.08	31.4
<i>Entandrophragma utile</i>	2	26.5	25.35
<i>Ficus exasperata</i>	2	27.9	18.5
<i>Funtumia africana</i>	25	21.54	23.34
<i>Guarea cedrata</i>	1	21.5	20
<i>Khaya ivorensis</i>	4	51.76	39.55
<i>Lophira alata</i>	1	96.3	48.1
<i>Lovoa trichilioides</i>	6	42.83	38.25
<i>Macaranga barteri</i>	5	23.62	21.3
<i>Mitragyna inermis</i>	20	21.98	24.72

<i>Monodora myristica</i>	13	27	23.42
<i>Monodora tenuifolia</i>	4	20.43	17.22
<i>Myrianthus arboreus</i>	18	22.11	20.11
<i>Nauclea diderrichi</i>	16	31.13	31.96
<i>Newbouldia leavis</i>	8	22.12	28.1
<i>Parkalina nitida</i>	6	17.23	17.67
<i>Pausinystalia yohimbe</i>	1	17.1	18.5
<i>Pentacletha macrophylla</i>	5	28.14	23.88
<i>Pycanthus angolensis</i>	9	44.26	34.16
<i>Rauvolfia vomitoria</i>	5	18.56	24.08
<i>Ricinodendron heudelotti</i>	3	46.9	37
<i>Rothmannia hispida</i>	3	23.23	23.27
<i>Sacoglottis gabonensis</i>	1	19.9	13
<i>Spondias mombins</i>	2	27	26.2
<i>Staudtia stipitata</i>	9	21.48	30.09
<i>Sterculia oblonga</i>	3	42.47	36.57
<i>Sterculia tragacantha</i>	9	18.96	23.99
<i>Strombosia grandifolia</i>	1	28.3	31.9
<i>Strombosia postulata</i>	12	23.08	23.73
<i>Terminalia ivorensis</i>	68	59.22	43.03
<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i>	4	19.52	24.86
<i>Trichilia monadelpha</i>	23	24.94	23.07
<i>Triplochiton scleroxylon</i>	2	85.35	39.15
<i>Voacanga africana</i>	8	19.2	17.05
<i>Xylopiya aethiopica</i>	1	15.9	13.4
<i>Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides</i>	3	20.27	23.57

3. 2. Diameter class distribution of trees in the two types of PAs

Stand structural diversity is characterized by Diameter at Breast Height (Dbh) and total tree height (Ali *et al*, 2016). A notable feature of mature natural forests is their Dbh distribution (Iyagin and Adekunle, 2017). The Dbh distribution differed between the two PA types (Fig. 4).

The decrease in number of trees with large Dbh is consistent with Osabiya *et al.*, 2022.

The scarcity of trees with large Dbh in both PAs can be attributed to their rarity as few tropical trees naturally grow to maturity and exploitation. The abundance of lower Dbh trees in Okomu National Park might indicate past selective extraction, whereas the higher number of medium Dbh trees in the Strict Nature Reserve of Akure might imply better protection and limited illegal harvesting (Iyagin and Adekunle, 2013, 2017).

Figure 3 shows the Dbh class distribution of trees in the two PAs. 317 of the 507 trees enumerated in the Okomu National Park were in the lower Dbh class of 15-24.9 cm while 117 of the 266 trees enumerated in the Strict Nature Reserve of Akure were in the Dbh class of 35-44.9 cm. There was tree in Dbh class > 75 cm in the Strict Nature Reserve of Akure while there were only 3 individual trees in that diameter class at the Okomu National Park. The figure also revealed that tree frequency reduces in the two PAs as the Dbh class increases.

Figure 4. Diameter class distribution of trees in the two types of PAs.

Table 3 presents statistical data comparing the mean height and mean diameter at breast height (Dbh) of tree species in the two PAs. The Mean Height for the Queen’s plot is 32.5 m while it is 26.84 under the Okomu National Park with a t-statistic of 1.96 at $p > 0.05$. The p-value is 0.056, which is slightly above the conventional threshold of 0.05 implies that the difference in mean height is not statistically significant at the 5% level.

The Mean Dbh in the Queen’s plot is 40.65 while it is 28.2 under the Okomu National Park with a t-statistic of 3.2 at $p > 0.05$. The p-value is 0.003, which is well below the 0.05 threshold. This indicates that the difference in mean Dbh is statistically significant.

Table 3. Independent t-test for tree growth variable of Height and Dbh under the two PAs types.

Growth variables	SNR	NP	T-test	Sign. Level
Mean Height	32.5	26.84	1.96	0.056
Mean Dbh	40.65	28.2	3.2	0.003

3. 3. Biodiversity metrics between the two types of PAs

The NP shows higher diversity indices ($H' = 3.47$; $1-D = 0.94$) compared to the SNR ($H' = 3.19$; $1-D = 0.93$), reflecting greater evenness and richness in the NP. High Shannon and Simpson indices in tropical forests are often associated with effective conservation strategies (Cazzola *et al.*, 2017).

The slight edge of the NP over the SNR might result from its larger size, which promote a wider range of ecological interactions. Conversely, the SNR focuses on strict protection, which may inadvertently limit species diversity by restricting certain ecological processes, such as natural disturbances that enhance species heterogeneity (Ali *et al.*, 2016).

Inferential statistics of paired t-test showed there was significant difference in the H' and SR of the two types of PAs studied. The slight differences in H' and SR between the two types of PAs could indicate varying degrees of disturbance, management objectives, or environmental factors influencing species composition. The higher species richness and diversity indices in Okomu National Park underscore its effectiveness in forest biodiversity conservation. The higher number of species and families in Okomu National Park could be attributed to its conservation objectives that emphasize multiple uses, contrasting with the stricter focus solely on conservation in the Queen’s plot. The H' index measures species diversity by accounting for both the abundance and evenness of species present. A higher H' value indicates greater diversity. The Queen’s plot has an H' value of 3.19, while Okomu National Park has a value of 3.47. Simpson's Diversity Index ($1-D$) measures diversity by focusing on the probability that two individuals randomly selected from a sample will belong to different species. Values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater diversity. The Queen’s plot has a $1-D$ value of 0.93, while Okomu National Park has a slightly higher value of 0.94.

Table 4. Summary of biodiversity metrics for the two PAs.

Protected Areas	No of individual tree	No. of Species	No. of Families	H'	1-D	SR
Strict Nature Reserve of Akure	266b	44a	21b	3.19b	0.93b	7.88a
Okomu National Park	507a	63b	28a	3.47a	0.94a	9.91b

Values with the same letter signifies there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$)

The Margalef Index (SR) measures species richness, reflecting the number of species present in an area relative to the number of individuals sampled. The Strict Nature Reserve of Akure has an SR of 7.88, whereas Okomu National Park has a higher SR of 9.91.

4. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that while SNRs are vital for conserving specific habitats and sensitive species, National Parks might be more effective in conserving overall biodiversity due to their larger size, habitat diversity, and more flexible management strategies. The study recommends integrated conservation approaches that combine strict protection with multi-use strategies to leverage their unique strength to maximize biodiversity outcomes.

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